

STRIDER NZAus

Statistical Analysis Plan

STRIDER (NZAus): A Randomised Controlled Trial of Sildenafil Therapy In Dismal Prognosis Early-Onset Intrauterine Growth Restriction (New Zealand and Australia).

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1. TRIAL HYPOTHESIS & AIMS

1.1 Hypothesis

The primary hypothesis is: sildenafil therapy compared to placebo therapy will increase the likelihood of increased fetal growth velocity (measured by change in abdominal circumference growth) in pregnancies complicated by severe early onset IUGR.

This hypothesis has been set in line with the STRIDER IPD Consortium.

1.2 Primary Aim

To assess the effect of sildenafil compared to placebo therapy on the proportion of pregnancies that have an increase in fetal growth velocity (measured by change in abdominal circumference growth) in pregnancies complicated by severe early onset IUGR.

This aim has been selected in line with the STRIDER IPD Consortium.

1.3 Secondary Aims

Effects on fetal growth and well-being:

1. To compare mean absolute change in abdominal circumference (mm) per day in fetuses treated with sildenafil and placebo.
2. To compare measures of uteroplacental, umbilical and fetal Doppler waveform studies in those treated with sildenafil and placebo.
3. To compare customised birthweight centiles in infants treated in-utero with sildenafil and placebo.

Effects on outcome:

1. To compare live-birth rates of infants treated in-utero with sildenafil and placebo.
2. To compare survival without major morbidity rates of infants treated in-utero with sildenafil and placebo.

To report frequency of adverse and serious adverse events associated with sildenafil use.

Myometrial and placental myography studies (Auckland Study Centre only):

1. To compare the effect of sildenafil and placebo on vascular endothelial and vascular smooth muscle cells in myometrium.
2. To compare the effect of sildenafil and placebo on chorionic plate and stem villous blood vessels within the placenta.

Analyses for myometrial and placental myography studies will be described separately.

2. STUDY DESIGN

STRIDER NZAus is a bi-national multicentre double blind randomised placebo controlled trial with intention-to-treat analysis.

2.1 Treatment groups

Women will be randomised to one of two groups:

1. *Sildenafil*
Oral sildenafil citrate 25mg three times daily (tds).
- OR
2. *Placebo*
Matching placebo tablets containing no active ingredient three times daily (tds).

2.3. RANDOMISATION

This will be performed using a web-based randomisation service operating at British Columbia Women's Hospital (Vancouver, Canada). Randomisation will be stratified for;

1. Gestational age at recruitment (< or $\geq 24+0$ weeks)
2. Present or absent/reversed end-diastolic flow in umbilical artery Doppler waveform.

Women will be randomised on a 1:1 ratio to sildenafil:placebo.

3. A Priori Statistical Methods

3.1 General statistical analyses consideration

Analyses will follow the principle of ITT. Data will be analysed according to the assigned treatment group at randomisation. Statistical models will adjust for the two randomisation variables, 'Gestational age at recruitment (< or $\geq 24+0$ weeks)' and 'Present or absent/reversed end-diastolic flow in umbilical artery Doppler waveform' unless otherwise stated. The effect of recruiting centres will be investigated and adjusted where appropriate (secondary outcomes of delivery and measures of neonatal outcome).

When the method of mixed model for repeated measure, MMRM, is used, the model will include treatment, time, treatment by time interaction, randomisation variables and baseline value as fixed effects, and subject as random effect, unless otherwise stated. The within-subject errors will be modelled using an appropriate covariance matrix. Candidate structures include but are not restricted to unstructured, autoregressive, Toeplitz, compound symmetry and spatial. Kenward-Roger method will be used to estimate the denominator degrees of freedom for fixed effects.

No imputation will be performed for missing data. No adjustment will be made for multiple comparisons. Number of days is calculated as (End Date – Start Date).

Two-sided p-values less than 0.05 will be used in determining statistical significance and all confidence intervals will be given at a two-sided 95% level unless otherwise stated.

3.2 Primary outcome – Proportion of pregnancies that have an increase in fetal growth velocity

Fetal growth velocity pre- and post- treatment will be compared. Fetal growth velocity will be determined by AC growth velocity based on Z-scores. INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standards¹ will be used to calculate Z-scores.

Pre-treatment growth velocity, $ACGV_{pre}$, will be calculated from: Z-score of the most recent AC measurement >12 days and Z-score of the recruitment AC measure. Where there is no previous scan with recorded AC, the AC will have been assumed to lie on the mean INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standard AC at 16 weeks gestation. Pre-treatment growth velocity data will be collected on CRF Form 3 Fetal Assessment, Before Treatment section.

Post-treatment growth velocity, $ACGV_{post}$, will be calculated from: Z-score of the recruitment AC measure and Z-score of the day 14 assessment AC measure, where delivery has occurred before the day 14 assessment the longest interval shall be used (day 10, day 5 day or finally 48 hour assessment). Post-treatment growth velocity data will be collected on CRF Form 5 Antenatal Maternal/Fetal Assessment, Fetal Assessment section.

The above method of calculating AC growth velocity differs from the method documented in the formal STRIDER NZAus Protocol (Version 4, December 2013) without any change in the documented primary outcome of “increase in fetal growth velocity”. INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standards were selected as the most appropriate AC growth measurement reference standard and Z-scores will be utilised in the calculation of growth velocity.

Dichotomised variable, $ACGV_{increase}$, which indicates whether there is an increase in AC growth velocity will be derived from comparing pre-treatment with post-treatment AC growth velocity. Logistic regression adjusted for the randomisation variables will be used to compare the treatment groups.

$$MeanIntG21_{AC}(GA) = -81.3243 + 11.6772GA - 0 \cdot 000561865 GA^3$$

$$SDIntG21_{AC}(GA) = -4 \cdot 36302 + 0 \cdot 121445 GA^2 - 0 \cdot 0130256 GA^3 + 0 \cdot 00282143 GA^3 \times \log(GA)$$

$$Z(GA) = \frac{AC_{GA} - MeanIntG21_{AC}(GA)}{SDIntG21_{AC}(GA)}$$

$$ACGV_{pre} = \frac{Z(GA_{Recruit}) - Z(GA_{Recent})}{GA_{Recruit} - GA_{Recent}}$$

$$ACGV_{Post} = \frac{Z(GA_{Longest}) - Z(GA_{Recruit})}{GA_{Longest} - GA_{Recruit}}$$

$$ACGV_{Increase} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } ACGV_{Post} > ACGV_{Pre} \\ 0, & \text{if } ACGV_{Post} \leq ACGV_{Pre} \end{cases}$$

GA	Gestational age (in weeks)
$MeanIntG21_{AC}(GA)$	Mean of the INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standards abdominal circumference at GA
$SDIntG21_{AC}(GA)$	Standard deviation of the INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standards abdominal circumference at GA
AC_{GA}	Abdominal circumference at GA
$Z(GA)$	Z-score at GA
GA_{Recent}	Gestational age (in weeks) when the most recent pre-treatment AC was measured at > 12 days
$GA_{Recruit}$	Gestational age (in weeks) at recruitment
$GA_{Longest}$	Gestational age (in weeks) at the day 14 assessment or the longest interval if delivery occurred before day 14 assessment
$ACGV_{Pre}$	Pre-treatment AC growth velocity
$ACGV_{Post}$	Post-treatment AC growth velocity
$ACGV_{Increase}$	Dichotomised increase in AC growth velocity variable
AC_{Recent}	Most recent AC measurement > 12 days, if no previous AC available mean INTERGROWTH-21 fetal growth standard AC at 16 weeks gestation will be used

3.3 Secondary outcomes

- Additional measures of fetal growth and wellbeing:
 - Growth velocity over the duration of study drug treatment via change in Z-score
Change in AC Z-score (change from baseline) measured at assessment points 48 hours, day 5, day 10, day 14, day 21 day, day 28 day etc (weekly from recruitment to stopping treatment) will be analysed with the method of mixed model for repeated measure, MMRM. In addition to the overall effect of treatment, the treatment comparison at day 14 assessment will be reported.
 - Mean birthweight
Descriptive statistics will be provided.

- Amniotic fluid index
AFI data will not be collected or analysed.
- Mean birthweight centile
Mean birthweight centile will be calculated using the GROW customised centile calculator².
Multiple linear regression method adjusted for randomisation variables will be used to compare birthweight centile between the two treatment groups.
- Deepest vertical amniotic fluid pocket
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- Short term variability (STV) measured by computerised cardiotocography (CTG)
Only centres with CTG will have STV data.
STV data will not be included in the primary analysis.
- Changes in uteroplacental, umbilical and fetal Doppler waveform studies:
 - Umbilical artery
 - PI
Higher PI indicates worse condition, for a normal pregnancy PI decrease over time. Umbilical artery PI will be analysed using MMRM method at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.
 - End diastolic flow
End diastolic flow data will not be included in the primary analysis.
 - Umbilical vein
Umbilical vein data will not be included in the primary analysis.
 - MCA PI
The method of MMRM will be used to analyse MCA PI at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.
 - MCA PSV
MCA PSV data will not be included in the primary analysis.
 - DV
 - PI
The method of MMRM will be used to analyse DV PI at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.

- a wave
DV a wave data will not be included in the primary analysis.
- Uterine artery
 - PI
The method of MMRM will be used to analyse Uterine artery PI at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.
 - Notch
Uterine artery notch data will not be included in the primary analysis.
- Maternal symptomatic hypotension, headaches and flushing
Summary statistics will be provided.
- Pre-eclampsia
 - New onset of pre-eclampsia
Descriptive statistics will be provided on the incidence of any new onset of pre-eclampsia during the study after randomisation.
 - Any preeclampsia
Descriptive statistics will be provided on the incidence of any pre-eclampsia during the study.
 - New severe pre-eclampsia
Descriptive statistics will be provided on the incidence of new onset of severe pre-eclampsia during the study after randomisation.
 - New use of antihypertensive agent
Descriptive statistics will be provided on the incidence of any new use of antihypertensives during the study after randomisation.
 - Use an any antihypertensive agent
Descriptive statistics will be provided on the incidence of any use of antihypertensives during the study.
 - Mean diastolic
The method of MMRM will be used to analyse pre- and post-treatment blood pressure at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.
 - Mean systolic blood pressure
The method of MMRM will be used to analyse pre- and post-treatment blood pressure at 48 hours, day 5, day 10 and day 14 assessments.
- Delivery
 - Randomisation-to-delivery interval

Randomisation-to-delivery interval will be analysed using linear regression method to compare treatments adjusting for randomisation variables, maternal pre-eclampsia anytime during pregnancy (Y/N), and recruiting centre if appropriate.

- Gestational age at delivery
Gestational age at delivery will be analysed using linear regression method to compare treatments adjusting for randomisation variables and recruiting centre if appropriate.
- Mode of delivery
Summary statistics will be provided.
- Indication for delivery
Summary statistics will be provided.
- Postpartum haemorrhage requiring transfusion.
Summary statistics will be provided.
- Measures of perinatal outcome
 - rates of live-births
Logistic regression will be used to compare the effect of treatment on the outcome of intrauterine death, adjusting for randomisation variables and recruiting centre if appropriate.
Descriptive statistics will be provided for intrauterine death and termination of pregnancy.
 - survival to hospital discharge
Any intrauterine or neonatal death prior to final neonatal discharge after birth will be classified as not survived to hospital discharge. Logistic regression will be used to compare the effect of treatment, adjusting for randomisation variables and recruiting centre if appropriate.
 - any major morbidity including the following severe adverse neonatal outcomes: chronic lung disease (bronchopulmonary dysplasia requiring ambulatory oxygen $\geq 36+0$ weeks corrected gestational age), severe central nervous system injury (intraventricular haemorrhage grade 3-4 or periventricular leukomalacia), \geq grade 3 retinopathy of prematurity requiring treatment or necrotising enterocolitis requiring surgery.
Logistic regression will be used to compare the effect of treatment, adjusting for randomisation variables, maternal pre-eclampsia anytime during pregnancy (Y/N) and recruiting centre if appropriate.

- survival free of major morbidity defined as survival free of severe adverse neonatal outcomes
Logistic regression will be used to compare the effect of treatment, adjusting for randomisation variables, maternal pre-eclampsia anytime during pregnancy (Y/N) and recruiting centre if appropriate.
- rates of bronchopulmonary dysplasia requiring ambulatory oxygen $\geq 36+0$ weeks corrected gestational age
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- rates of intraventricular haemorrhage grade 3-4
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- rates of periventricular leukomalacia
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- rates of \geq grade 3 retinopathy of prematurity requiring treatment
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- rates of necrotising enterocolitis requiring surgery
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- use of surfactant
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- use of ventilator and number of ventilator days
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- use of supplemental oxygen and number of supplemental oxygen days
Descriptive statistics will be provided.
- number of days to full feeds.
Time to full feeds will not be analysed.
- Any adverse or serious adverse events.
Descriptive statistics and listing will be provided.

4. References

1. PAPAGEORGHIOU AT, OHUMA EO, ALTMAN DG, et al. International standards for fetal growth based on serial ultrasound measurements: the Fetal Growth Longitudinal Study of the INTERGROWTH-21st Project. Lancet 2014;384:869-79.
2. GARDOSI J, FRANCIS A. Customised Weight Centile Calculator. GROW v6.7 (UK) 2013 Gestation Network, www.gestation.net. 2013.

Amendments made to version 3 (10th July 2017) – highlighted through text